

From Tomographic Imaging to Numerical Simulations: An Open-Source Workflow for True Morphology Mesoscale FE Meshes

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Cover Figure

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21 **Abstract**

22 Full-field techniques such as tomography are becoming progressively more
 23 central in the study of complex phenomena, in particular where
 24 spatiotemporal evolution is crucial, as in moisture transport or crack
 25 initiation in porous media. These techniques provide a unique insight in
 26 the local process whose quantification allows the improvement of our
 27 understanding and of the models describing them. Nevertheless, the model
 28 validation can be pushed further by attempting to explicitly represent the
 29 heterogeneities and simulate their role in the processes. Once validated,
 30 these models can be used to perform “virtual experiments”, and overcome
 31 the limitations of the experiments (e.g., sample size and number, fine

32 control of the boundary and initial conditions). This study proposes a
33 connection between tomography images and mesoscale models through a
34 workflow that mainly employs open-source tools. This workflow is
35 illustrated through the digitization of a Portland cement concrete sample,
36 stemming from neutron tomographies and resulting in a numerical finite
37 element mesh. The proposed workflow is flexible, allowing for the
38 conversion of images from various sources, such as x-ray or neutron
39 tomographies, to different numerical representations of the domain, such
40 as finite element meshes or even a discrete domain required by discrete
41 element methods, while preserving real morphologies with an accuracy
42 proportionate to the specific need of the problem. Beside its
43 generalizability, our method also offers automated labelling of the different
44 domains and boundaries in both the volumetric and surface meshes, which
45 is often necessary for assigning material properties and boundary
46 conditions. Finally, the series of image, geometry and mesh processing steps
47 described in this work are made available on a GitHub repository.

48 **Keywords:** Conformal Meshing, Concrete Mesostructure, Mesoscale
49 Modelling, Neutron Imaging

50

51 1. Introduction

52 ~~The properties of materials at structural scale are determined by the~~
53 ~~interplay of physical phenomena which takes place at multiple length scales~~
54 ~~[1]. Such mechanisms can be found at sizes of different orders of magnitude~~
55 ~~ranging from the interatomic bonding of its elements and molecules,~~

56 through the microstructure until reaching its shape and geometrical
57 features [1].

58 The purpose of considering the interaction of such different phenomena in
59 a simulation of the variation of the physico-chemical properties at a certain
60 scale is to understand their collective response and the role played by the
61 heterogeneity at the scale above. This is specially true in multiple crucial
62 topics that involve complex processes that dictate the response of the
63 system and that encompass an array of length scales spanning different
64 characteristic sizes, such as the description of the mechanics of a tumor
65 growth [2], or that of the concrete structure damage under a fire accident
66 [3].

67 Multiscale materials showcase diverse characteristics at various levels of
68 observation, often requiring consideration of multiple scales to
69 comprehensively describe their behavior [1]. Concrete for instance, a
70 subcategory of geomaterials, is considered as a multiscale material due to
71 its complex structure and properties that emerge from interactions across
72 multiple length scales. Three length scales can at least be considered for
73 this material: the microscale, the mesoscale and the macroscale. At the
74 microscale, concrete comprises cement paste, aggregates, and voids, with
75 interactions between cement particles and water, hydration product
76 formation shaping its microstructure. Moving to the mesoscale, elements
77 like aggregate arrangements, pore distribution, the interfacial transition
78 zone (ITZ), micro-cracks play pivotal roles. At the macroscale, concrete's
79 properties, including compressive and tensile strength, elasticity, and
80 thermal behavior, emerge from the cumulative effects of micro and
81 mesoscale structures and their interactions.

82 ~~When it comes to modeling concrete behavior (for instance, or any~~
83 ~~heterogenous media), most of the models proposed in the literature assume~~
84 ~~a homogeneous material and overlook the description of the local impact~~
85 ~~of the heterogeneity while simulating the overall response. In fact, most of~~
86 ~~the models display a sophisticated mathematical formulation to describe~~
87 ~~the averaged energy, mass, and momentum transfer at the macroscopic~~
88 ~~level. Meanwhile, mesoscopic models take explicitly into account specific~~
89 ~~features of the material's microstructure such as the presence of aggregates~~
90 ~~and macro pores. It follows that at this scale, the mesh should represent~~
91 ~~three domains: the macro pores, the aggregates domains, and the~~
92 ~~homogenized mortar phase made out of cement paste and sand fines. The~~
93 ~~rationale behind such partitioning is to represent the effect of those~~
94 ~~heterogeneities (strain incompatibility, modified hydric properties, etc)~~
95 ~~that might have a consequential impact on the Thermo-Hydro-Mechanical~~
96 ~~(THM) local processes. For instance, many pieces of evidence suggest that~~
97 ~~the shapes and sizes of these heterogeneous components have a non-~~
98 ~~negligible effect on the stress field and the cracking patterns [4]. In turn,~~
99 ~~those cracking patterns contribute to thermo-hydric local variations such~~
100 ~~as an increase in the local permeability [5].~~

101 Many studies in the literature highlight the role of mesostructure on the
102 overall behavior of concrete undergoing different types of loading. Those
103 studies especially emphasize the role of strain incompatibilities between the
104 cement matrix and the aggregates on mechanical behavior [2], micro-cracks
105 formation [3], failure mechanisms [4, 5] damage under fire accidents [6], the
106 effect of cracks on the local permeability [7], etc. Besides experimental
107 evidence, mathematical models developed at the mesoscale are of a great

108 benefit to enhance the predictive capacity of numerical approaches. In fact,
109 most of the models at the macroscale display a complex mathematical
110 formulation to describe the averaged energy, mass, and momentum transfer
111 of a homogenized material. Mesoscale models are useful, not only to
112 simulate processes at the mesoscale, but also to help parameterize and
113 validate macroscale models. This can be done either by simple calibration
114 or by use of sophisticated upscaling and homogenization techniques [8, 9].
115 In addition, mesoscale models can also be used to propose
116 phenomenological behavior laws that capture the impact of local processes
117 [10].

118 It follows that mesoscopic models require a non-homogeneous material field
119 and that the generated mesh should account for multiple domains. In
120 addition to the homogenized mortar phase (accounting for the sand fines
121 and cement paste), other domains could be added such as aggregates,
122 macro-pores, ITZ, *etc.* It should be noted that the impact of the explicit
123 representation of some of the domains is still disputed in the literature and
124 is highly dependent on the type of physics to be modelled. For instance,
125 while the ITZ may play an important role in mechanical simulation, its
126 relevance in certain moisture transfer contexts may be deemed negligible
127 [11]. In addition, there is no agreement on how to model this domain (zero-
128 thickness cohesive element) or what thickness should be attributed to it
129 [12, 13].

130 Previous studies at the mesoscale suggest different methods to build the
131 required multi-domain mesh. In [14], the generated mesostructure of the
132 aggregates consisted of diameter-varying disks/spheres and their variation
133 followed an experimental particle size distribution curve, thus respecting

134 the volume fraction of aggregates in the concrete volume. However, the
135 simplification in the aggregates shape overlooks the influence of their true
136 morphology. In addition, no explicit modeling of the ITZ is considered
137 despite its proven effect on the failure mechanism in mechanical
138 simulations. In [15], a THM model is introduced featuring spherical
139 aggregates and a weak interface transition zone (ITZ) to simulate concrete
140 behavior. However, neither the particle size distribution nor their shape
141 was accurately accounted for, raising concerns about the model's
142 representativeness in simulating real concrete materials. In [4], a simple
143 and straightforward mapping scheme between a XCT¹-informed voxelized
144 mesostructure and a regular cubic mesh is proposed. In fact, this approach
145 involves transforming each voxel into eight-noded hexahedral cubic
146 elements. Consequently, directly operating on the initial tomography data
147 is not feasible due to the resulting excessive element count. To address
148 this, compressing the image (scaling it down) becomes necessary in order
149 to decrease the voxel count. However, this compression introduces
150 inaccuracies in representing the volume fractions of the segmented phases,
151 demanding meticulous sensitivity analysis to determine the appropriate
152 compression level. In Stamati et al. [16], a projection-based method of a
153 trinary segmentation of a XCT on a tetrahedral mesh is proposed. The
154 resulting mesh is however non-conformal and results in having shared mesh
155 elements between the different domains. This necessitates non-
156 conventional FE techniques capable of managing strong discontinuities,
157 like the Extended or the Embedded Finite Element Method (XFEM and

¹ x-ray Computed Tomography

158 EFEM, respectively). On the other hand, the formulation of those methods
159 are especially beneficial to predict crack initiation and propagation and can
160 be parameterized with only a few number of parameters easily identified
161 through conventional experiments. ~~In [10], a fully-coupled meso-scale THM~~
162 ~~model is proposed, though with only a single ellipsoidal aggregate.~~ In [10],
163 a fully-coupled meso-scale THM model is proposed to study the effect of a
164 single big aggregate on the overall behaviour of a mortar sample. However,
165 the conformal mesh used in this study was generated between a volume-
166 equivalent ellipsoid and a cylinder since the big aggregate was oval-like
167 shaped. No workflow was therefore proposed by the authors to transition
168 from the tomography to the conformal mesh. Finally, a weakly-coupled
169 THM mesoscale model is proposed in [17] that applied a similar mapping
170 scheme to that in [4], however, this time the mesostructure ~~is~~ was obtained
171 after a series of image processing steps applied to the original neutron
172 tomography.

173 With the increasing number of experiments that employ advanced imaging
174 techniques such as (but not limited to) x-ray and neutron tomography (see
175 for instance the following literature reviews [18, 19, 20] and the following
176 studies at low-temperature [21], moderate temperature [22], high
177 temperature [23, 24, 25] and cracked medium [26], *etc*), there is a need to
178 propose a method that bridges the experimental-numerical gap between
179 ~~arbitrarily complex heterogeneous 3D images and 3D morphology-~~
180 ~~conserving Finite Element meshes~~ complex heterogeneous 3D images
181 obtained by tomography experiments and the 3D morphology-conserving
182 digital representation of such features using multi-domain FE meshes. This
183 work presents two possible pipelines for this purpose (a hybrid,

184 predominantly MATLAB-based approach and a full Python approach) to
185 accomplish this objective. To illustrate that, the step-by-step series of
186 image-processing and computational geometry methods devised on the
187 workflows are applied to a neutron tomography of a concrete sample
188 tomography to obtain a conformal multi-domain mesh that can be used for
189 FE applications.

190 **2. Material and Methods**

191 *2.1. General Workflow*

192 The example used in this communication is that of a concrete sample that
193 underwent THM processes while being scanned using x-ray and neutron
194 tomography simultaneously. The concrete mixture is composed of cement,
195 sand, gravels and water. The detailed composition of the sample is
196 described in [22].

197 The neutron tomography of the concrete sample was acquired at the
198 NeXT-Grenoble beamline [27]. Specifically, 900 projections were acquired
199 over a 360° rotation. All the image acquisition parameters are detailed in
200 [22] and the data can be found at [https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-](https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.UGA-60)
201 [DATA.UGA-60](https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.UGA-60). The sets of radiographies were then reconstructed into the
202 corresponding 3D volumes by means of the Feldkamp (FDK) back
203 projection algorithm, as implemented in the commercial software X-act
204 (from RX-solutions). Besides the aforementioned medianing of the
205 radiographies, some small corrections for beam hardening were also applied
206 during the reconstruction step.

207 The reconstructed image can be seen as 3D neutron attenuation field where
208 the aggregates have a lower neutron attenuation ~~then~~ **than** the surrounding
209 mortar matrix (cement paste and sand fines which shape is not detectable
210 by the image resolution) due to their distinct water content, as seen in
211 Figure 1a). In fact, water molecules heavily attenuate neutrons due to the
212 presence of Hydrogen element (which has a very strong interaction with
213 neutrons). Therefore, based on the distinct gray value between the
214 aggregates and the surrounding mortar, an intensity-based segmentation is
215 used to separate between these two components.

216 It should be noted that in the case presented herein, the focus is to
217 obtain a mesh considering only ~~large~~ **coarser** aggregates (with an equivalent
218 spherical radius of 4mm or more, as seen in the particle size distribution
219 curves presented in Figure 1 d), where the sieved image is compared to the
220 original image), hence, the distinction between pores and aggregates is not
221 required, as the former ~~is~~ **are way smaller than the threshold size**.
222 Simultaneous segmentation of the pores and aggregates exist in the
223 literature, such as the multimodal analysis of neutron ~~from~~ **and** x-ray
224 tomographies as obtained in the NeXT equipment, and described by
225 Roubin et al. [28].

226 The result of this operation is a binary image of the aggregates, as
227 shown in Figure 1 b). However, since the sand and gravels granulometry
228 ranges from fractions of a millimeter to **several** millimeters, the binary
229 image shows sand particles which shape is represented by a few voxels only.
230 This largely increases the computational cost of the meshing process, as a
231 consequence, discarding small sand fines is needed for practical purposes.
232 A possible solution for this is to use watershed algorithms to label each

233 particle and characterize it by its equivalent spherical radius, as seen in
234 the sequence of Figures 1 c), e) and f). In this study, the specific value of
235 4mm was chosen somewhat arbitrarily to establish a cutoff. Below this
236 threshold, the aggregates were not treated as separate entities; rather, their
237 collective influence was integrated into the behaviour of the homogenized
238 mortar phase. It is also important to highlight that the accuracy of the
239 method is partly function of the richness of the image of origin. The
240 approach proposed herein is, in this respect, agnostic to the origin of the
241 image (e.g., Neutron, x-ray or magnetic resonance imaging) and its quality.
242 The *required* accuracy is, conversely a function of the specific application,
243 e.g. some first order description of the shape of grains (in the order of
244 tens/hundreds of microns) in granular media seem to be sufficient to
245 capture some of the more salient aspects of the process [29], but a much
246 richer description and smaller scales is known to be needed for crack
247 propagation in crystalline solids. Furthermore, there may be a necessity for
248 a meticulous sensitivity analysis concerning the threshold value in certain
249 scenarios, such as mechanical failure simulations. Additionally, it's
250 imperative to rigorously assign the effective properties of the homogenized
251 phase.

252 However, as observed by the authors during the analysis, the
253 performance of the watershed algorithm in separating each aggregate
254 individually is not flawless and some small particles can be mistakenly
255 associated to a large particle in some cases. To remove those persistent
256 particles, denoising filters (despeckle filter) or binary operations (a series
257 of erode-dilate operations) can be used.

258 The next step is to downscale the denoised binary image - resulting in the
259 representation present in Figure 1 g) - and to apply a marching cube
260 algorithm to obtain a surface mesh of the aggregates. A 3D surface
261 smoothing algorithm is then applied to smooth the voxelized morphology
262 of the aggregates, as depicted in Figure 1 h). Additional processing steps
263 can sometimes be required in order to fix the surface mesh (in case it is
264 not watertight, or it presents intersecting shells problems or even if it
265 requires remeshing, *etc*).

266 Finally, the aggregates surface mesh can be imported to a capable meshing
267 software or library to generate the multi-domain tetrahedral mesh, as
268 shown in Figure 1 i). A labelling step of the different mesh surfaces might
269 be needed to assign the boundary conditions of the yet-to-be-solved
270 numerical problem, this can be observed in Figure 1 j).

271 The full pipeline that includes the different image, geometry and mesh
272 processing steps can be visualized in Figure 1.

273 *2.2. Detailed Workflow 1: Hybrid MATLAB-Python (HMP) approach*

274 This first approach is a hybrid one that uses Python scripts for the
275 preliminary imaging processing of the tomography and for the mesh format
276 conversion, and that relies heavily on a MATLAB toolbox called GIBBON
277 (The Geometry and Image-Based Bioengineering add-On) [30]. GIBBON
278 is an open-source MATLAB toolbox that includes CAD, geometry and
279 image processing tools. This toolbox interfaces free open source softwares
280 such as TetGen [31] that possesses quality meshing capabilities. A
281 MATLAB license is required for this part of the proposed methodology.

282 After reconstruction, the aggregates and the sand particles are easily
283 distinguishable from their surrounding matrix given their distinct
284 attenuation value (see Figure 1 a)). It follows that applying a simple
285 intensity-based threshold is sufficient to segment the aggregates in the raw
286 image. This operation is basic and can be performed in any software or
287 library with image processing capabilities, resulting in Figure 1 b).

288 As mentioned in the previous section, the small aggregates which have a
289 sphere-equivalent diameter below an arbitrary value of 4mm for instance
290 are to be removed. This was possible by applying a watershed algorithm
291 [32] which labels individual sand and aggregates particles - shown in Figure
292 1 c) - and assign a sphere-equivalent diameter to each one of them. In this
293 work, this operation was done using the SPAM Python package [33].

294 The previous operation, although very effective and capable of removing
295 most of the aggregates below 4mm, allows some small particles to be
296 mistakenly attributed to large particles (see for instance the difference
297 between Figure 1 f) and Figure 1 g) ~~as smaller speckles are removed~~ **as**
298 **smaller ones are removed**). To get rid of these impurities, multiple
299 denoising filters could be used such as the despeckle filter or by simply
300 applying multiple Erode-Dilate operations. Multiple softwares and
301 packages provide implementation of such filters and binary operations. In
302 this work, the despeckle filter implementation of ImageJ software [34] was
303 used and was applied multiple times.

304 The binary image was then downscaled and a Marching Cubes
305 Algorithm [35] was applied on the processed binary image to extract the
306 outer shell of the aggregates. The resulting surface mesh is then smoothed
307 using SurfaceSmooth function [36] from the MATLAB file exchange,

308 leading to the surface mesh shown in Figure 1 h). Alternative functions in
309 GIBBON such as PatchSmooth can also be used for this purpose with two
310 possible smoothing methods (Laplacian or Humphreys-Classes smoothing).

311 It should be noticed that these algorithms are parametrized enabling
312 thorough control of the process, and thus it may require trial-and-error
313 tests for selecting the appropriate set of parameters to balance the
314 smoothing properly and achieve representative geometries. The complexity
315 of this stage can be also related to the shape of the aggregate as rounded
316 natural ones (such as the ones considered in the example presented in this
317 work) are easier to smooth than artificial grinded raw material with sharp
318 edges.

319 Once the aggregates surface mesh is smoothed, we create a cylindrical
320 surface mesh and we use the TetGen [31] GIBBON interface to create the
321 multi-domain tetrahedral conformal mesh illustrated by Figure 1 i).

322 Finally, the mesh can be converted to multiple formats using the meshio
323 library [37].

324 We note that all of the described steps in this pipeline are available on the
325 GitHub repository at [https://github.com/TomoToFE/supp_code_](https://github.com/TomoToFE/supp_code_mesoscale_mesh)
326 [mesoscale_mesh](https://github.com/TomoToFE/supp_code_mesoscale_mesh).

327 *2.3. Detailed Workflow 2: a Python-based approach*

328 The current workflow is proposed as a completely open-source
329 alternative to Workflow 1. It presents the advantage of having all the
330 required steps within a single software, from the tomography image to the
331 finite element mesh. If a Python package is used for the numerical modeling

332 stage, the whole process can be set up on a single reproducible
333 environment. ~~As a drawback, the functionalities required for the whole~~
334 ~~process have multiple dependencies, which nonetheless cause no conflict.~~
335 ~~However, all of them can be used simultaneously and within the same~~
336 ~~environment, without any dependency conflicts.~~ One potential downside
337 when constructing a pipeline using multiple libraries is the possibility of
338 encountering compatibility issues such as namespace collisions or version
339 conflicts. Nevertheless, all the packages herein can operate simultaneously
340 within the same environment without facing any dependency conflicts.

341 The process starts with the reconstructed tomographies stored as a stack
342 of files .tiff. Due to faster load times and the possibility of compression,
343 the stack is converted to a .npz file based on the NumPy Python library
344 [38]. Next, the same image processing applied in Workflow 1 is applied,
345 starting from the segmentation of the different phases through
346 thresholding the image and following with the labeling of each individual
347 aggregate through the watershed algorithm of [32], shown in Figures 1 b)
348 and 1 c), respectively.

349 The next step in the workflow is the removal of smaller aggregates that
350 were mistakenly labeled as a part of a larger aggregate
351 (undersegmentation). In order to do so a succession of erode-dilate
352 operations is applied to the image. In the proposed pipeline, the
353 tomography image stored as a NumPy array is cast in a UniformGrid
354 object from the PyVista library [39]. It should be mentioned that the
355 SPAM library or scikit-image [40] can be employed as well; however, as
356 further steps will take advantage of functionalities of PyVista, the current

357 methodology adopts the PyVista implementation of the erosion-dilation
358 process, as a mean to reduce the number of transitions between distinct
359 Python libraries. As a bonus, the PyVista library enables the fast rendering
360 of tridimensional images within the Python integrated development
361 environment (IDE).

362 Next, with the tomography image comprising only the aggregates whose
363 sizes lie in the range of the mesoscale feature of interest, a marching cubes
364 algorithm is utilized to obtain a surface mesh from the aggregates. It should
365 be noted that because of the PyVista implementation of the marching
366 cubes' algorithm, some aggregates are not watertight, and some holes on
367 the surface mesh of the aggregates are observable. PyVista itself has a
368 functionality that can fill holes, however, depending on the hole size, the
369 surface mesh can be coarse at such regions, which can pose problems in the
370 finite element mesh generation step.

371 Thus, the PyMeshFix library [41] is used to fill the holes and performing
372 a refinement of the region that is patched. After that, the surface mesh can
373 be recast as PyVista PolyData object and each aggregate can be separated
374 as independent submeshes.

375 The next stage aims to create .stl files for each aggregate for loading within
376 the Gmsh software [42], this can be done using PyVista, which can also be
377 used for performing surface smoothing on the aggregates. The researcher
378 can choose to either apply a Laplacian smoothing or a method based on
379 Taubin's algorithm, which is the one selected in the current workflow due
380 to its volume-preserving capability, which leads to Figure 1 h). This stage
381 can be optional depending on the features of the structure that is being

382 analyzed. For natural aggregates, for instance, this step is less relevant
383 than for objects containing tubular geometries with sharp corners.

384 This stage also can highlight the flexibility of the proposed workflow which
385 allows to simply alter the geometry of features of interest, for example to
386 assess the role of one or more heterogeneities in the system, which would
387 be virtually impossible experimentally.

388 Finally, with all the .stl files from each individual aggregate, Gmsh can
389 be used to create the overall structure of the object, mark the external
390 boundaries, and most importantly, the internal boundaries between matrix
391 and aggregates, and the whole domain can be meshed. Local mesh
392 refinement can be applied with the information on the internal boundaries,
393 resulting in Figure 1 i). This can also be crucial for different numerical
394 models, as it might be required to define constitutive laws that represent
395 the interfacial transition zone between the different phases.

396 Finally, as proposed in Workflow 1, the mesh can be converted to the
397 format required for the numerical method tool of choice, by also using the
398 meshio library [37].

399
 400 Figure 1: Individual stages of the general workflow, starting from a) the neutron
 401 tomography image, b) the segmented phases, c) the labeled aggregates, d) the digital
 402 sieving of the aggregates, e) the sieved aggregates larger than 4mm, f) the relabelled
 403 image, g) resulting image after erosion-dilation process, h) the surface mesh, and, finally,
 404 i) the obtained volumetric mesh with j) the detail of the mortar and aggregates.

405 3. Conclusions

406 Heterogeneity plays a crucial role in multiple processes. Nonetheless,
407 traditionally the material response is simulated neglecting this
408 heterogeneity because of a lack of insight in their role as well as to simplify
409 the numerical formulation. Additionally, limitations on available
410 techniques hindered the observation and comprehension of the dynamics
411 of such process *in-situ*.

412 Currently, though, such context changed, and the current work proposes a
413 streamlined open-source workflow to obtain finite element meshes from
414 tomography images. This setup enables mesoscale analysis on an arbitrary
415 number of features of interest.

416 The novelty of the methods proposed herein lies on the flexibility and
417 simplicity of the tools, as the same process can be extended to different
418 fields of application, as well as considering different tomography images
419 (such as x-rays instead of neutrons), ~~or even the mathematical models that~~
420 ~~will be used for the simulation of the process, such as discrete techniques~~
421 ~~as discrete element modelling (DEM), instead of the often adopted~~
422 ~~continuum approaches as the finite element method (FEM).~~ or even the
423 mathematical models that will be used for the simulation of the process,
424 such as both continuum approaches such as FEM, or even the discrete
425 techniques as discrete element modelling (DEM). [In the case of DEM, not](#)
426 [exemplified in the workflows presented herein, the required representation](#)
427 [of the microstructures is achieved by exporting the features of interest](#)
428 [\(such as the aggregates\) in .stl files that can be converted and imported](#)
429 [by the simulation software. This enables the creation of assemblies](#)

430 comprising spherical particles of equivalent volume, achievable through
431 standard DEM techniques, or the utilization of aggregates reflecting their
432 authentic morphology, possible in the scope of more sophisticated DEM
433 techniques. Finally, all the code is documented and available at GitHub
434 for the reader
435 (at https://github.com/TomoToFE/supp_code_mesoscale_mesh),
436 making its adoption to anyone readily available regardless of one's level of
437 expertise in the fields of imaging and numerical simulations, which
438 previously posed a complex learning curve to such analysis.

439 **4. Supplementary Code**

440 The supplementary code for the workflows can be found in the following
441 GitHub repository:
442 https://github.com/TomoToFE/supp_code_mesoscale_mesh, while the
443 considered data can be found at ([https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-](https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.UGA-60)
444 [DATA.UGA-60](https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.UGA-60)).

445 **5. Acknowledgments**

446 The authors acknowledge the support of the French *Agence Nationale de*
447 *la Recherche* (ANR) (project MULTI-FIRE ANR-23-CE51-0001-01) and
448 the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior - Brasil
449 (CAPES) – Finance Code 001. The authors would like to thank the
450 Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo - FAPESP (grant
451 numbers: 2021/002510 and 2022/12406-0). The authors are also grateful
452 for the funding from Cancer Research UK (CRUK C44767/A29458).

453 **6. Authorship statement (CRediT)**

454 **Hani Cheikh Sleiman:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software,

455 Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft

456 **Murilo Henrique Moreira:** Methodology, Software, Data curation,

457 Writing – original draft **Alessandro Tengattini:** Resources, Validation,

458 Writing – review & editing **Stefano Dal Pont:** Conceptualization,

459 Investigation, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing

460

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